

Use of valence delta, δ^v in the molecular connectivity calculations and correlation with molar refraction

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Manuscript received 4 February 2008, revised 18 August 2008, accepted 19 December 2008

Abstract : Molecular connectivity calculations have been carried out for highly anisotropic bidentate ligands (C_{2v} symmetry), organometallic substrates of the formulae, R_2MX_2 (where R is an alkyl group and X is a halogen atom) and organometallic chelates of the formulae, R_2ML_x (where L is a bidentate ligand). Multiple Chi, ${}^m\chi_t^v$ with reference to valence delta, δ^v have been calculated for the hydrogen suppressed graphs (skeletal structures) for each molecule and have been correlated with molar refractions. These correlations will play a vital role in the SAR studies of biologically active molecules.

Keywords : Molecular connectivity, organometallics, ligands, molar refraction, chelates, conformational analysis.

Introduction

Organometallic compounds having high anisotropy have been a matter of interest to chemists for the last two decades. Preliminary studies made by Saksena and Nelson¹ on the light scattering by bidentate ligands suggest that the ligands can be used as probes in deciding conformation of chelates of the formulae, R_2ML_x , where L^- is an anisotropic bidentate ligand and M is the central metal atom.

Many bidentate ligands e.g. 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine)² and salicylic acid³ show antibacterial action with many drugs during chelation. Chelates of 2,2'-bipyridyl show marked *curariform* action⁴. In designing a chelate of biological importance, organometallic moieties, R_2M^{n+} play a vital role in SAR. There are many organometallic halides⁵, which retain their *cis* structure even after coordination, act as *agonist* molecules and show marked biological activities.

Structural and conformational studies based on the principle of additivity and transferability of bond-polarisability components of chelate molecules have been reported separately⁶.

The concept of molecular connectivity was developed by Randic^{7,9} by utilising graph theory. Every hydrogen

suppressed graph (skeletal structure) can be formulated in to a topological matrix to a HMO matrix⁸, in which the non-diagonal elements are vertex valences, δ_1 and δ^v (valence atom) in case of hetero atoms. The use of connectivity index in correlations with pharmacological actions has been discussed in detail by Kier and Hall^{10,11}. The conformation of a molecule provides a specificity with regard to the receptor molecule in the biophase. A particular conformation¹² of a molecule can be adsorbed at a particular site on the receptor molecule (of a tissue, membrane or cell wall) giving rise to an optimum biological activity. The valence δ^v terms for hetero atom improve the quality of correlation of ${}^m\chi_t^v$ terms (molecular connectivity of subgraph terms using δ^v) with molar refraction, R_m in comparison to χ and ${}^m\chi_t$ terms (molecular connectivity using vertex valence, δ_1). All these terms have been widely described in the literature cited above. QSAR studies carried out in recent years are being used in modifying structures¹³.

Experimental and computed R_m data

Bousch and Lomb Model 33-45-03 series 021 precision refractometer has been calibrated by KCl solutions of known strength in water at 25 ± 0.1 °C. A NBE Ultrathermostat has been used to circulate water in cell

jacket. A He-Ne laser of 3 mW has been used as light source. The precision in n is of the order of ± 0.00001 . Density measurements have been made on a Westphal-type balance in the temperature controlled at 25 ± 0.1 °C. The error in d is of the order of 0.1%. The data of calibration of differential refractometer, molar refraction and density measurements for diorganotin dichlorides and highly anisotropic ligands⁵ are already reported earlier. Values of molar refraction for organotin(IV) and thallium(III) chelates have been computed from the additivity of bond refraction in a molecule and have been reported in an earlier publication¹⁴.

Table 1. Molar refraction and ${}^m\chi_t^v$ terms for stepwise multiple regression analysis (substrates)

Sl. no.	Substrates	R_m (Obsd.) ^b (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	${}^1\chi$	${}^1\chi^v$	${}^2\chi^v$	${}^3\chi_p^v$
1.	(Et) ₂ .SnCl ₂	33.91	3.12	2.64	1.24	0.52
2.	(Et) ₂ .SnO ^d	28.55	2.81	2.45	1.26	0.73
3.	(Et) ₂ .TiCl ^d	28.89	2.62	2.53	0.99	0.54
4.	(Bu) ₂ .SnCl ₂	50.98	5.12	4.49	2.72	1.26
5.	(Bu) ₂ .SnO ^d	45.62	4.62	4.47	2.57	1.41
6.	(<i>n</i> -Oct) ₂ .SnCl ₂	85.13	7.91	8.50	5.22	3.43
7.	(<i>n</i> -Oct) ₂ .SnO ^d	79.77	8.41	8.32	3.37	3.52

^a R_m Calcd. is determined by the feedback of variables.

^b R_m Obsd. has been taken as the R_D value from the bond refraction additivity, other values have been experimentally determined (Ref. 20).

$$R_m = -1.8683 {}^1\chi + 25.5770 {}^1\chi^v - 2.0283 {}^2\chi^v - 27.4387 {}^1\chi_p^v - 13.7703.$$

$$n = 7, r = 0.9979, s = 2.3507e - 03, \text{ P.E. in } r = 3.9232e - 04.$$

Theoretical calculations of ${}^m\chi_t$ and ${}^m\chi_t^v$ terms :

In its initial formulation Randic's Scheme is suited for hydrogen suppressed graphs of hydrocarbons. The connectivity index between two vertices v_i and v_j can be written as

$$\chi = (\delta_i \cdot \delta_j)^{-1/2} \quad (1)$$

Hence, χ , is a bond index depending on the local branching in a molecule. The total molecular connectivity is equal to $\Sigma \chi$ i.e. sum of all bond connectivity indices. The hydrogen suppressed graphs known as skeletal structures are first labelled by vertex valence δ_i and also labelled with ${}^1\chi$ terms per bond. The ${}^m\chi_t$ terms, the so called higher connectivity indices can be defined as,

$${}^m\chi_t = \sum_G \prod_i^{m+1} (\delta_i)^{-1/2} \quad (2)$$

where the sum is over connected path subgraphs with m edges, the product is over the vertices constituting subgraphs G and δ_i is the valence of vertex i in a hydrogen suppressed graph. All details of calculation and a few relationships have been described²⁰. While evaluating ${}^m\chi_t$ terms, all bonds are considered to be single bonds. The hetero atoms, metallic or non-metallic have been retained in the hydrogen suppressed subgraphs and vertex valence, δ_i are calculated in the same way as has been done for a carbon atom in hydrocarbons. This is an extension of the original concept given by Randic in this scheme. In evaluating ${}^1\chi$ for cyclic molecules, 0.5 is subtracted for each

Table 2. Molar refraction and ${}^m\chi_t^v$ for stepwise multiple regression analysis (ligands)

Sl. no.	Ligands	R_m (Obsd.) (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	${}^1\chi$	${}^1\chi^v$	${}^2\chi^v$	${}^3\chi_p^v$
1.	Dibenzoyl methane	63.91	7.73	7.77	3.12	1.63
2.	Tropolone	36.42	3.86	3.68	1.26	0.63
3.	8-Hydroxyquinoline	37.48	4.38	4.87	1.95	0.79
4.	Salicylaldehyde	36.94	4.05	3.71	1.74	0.62
5.	2,2'-Bipyridine	42.41	3.97	4.27	1.86	0.83
6.	Acetyl acetone	26.89	3.48	2.88	1.56	0.83
7.	1,10'-Phenanthroline	61.05	5.86	6.56	2.32	1.12

$$R_m = 0.8874 {}^1\chi + 8.9888 {}^1\chi^v - 6.7326 {}^2\chi^v + 9.3245.$$

$$n = 7, r = 0.9672, s = 0.0323, \text{ P.E. in } r = 6.2144e - 03.$$

Table 3. Molar refraction and ${}^m\chi_t^v$ terms for stepwise multiple regression analysis ($R_2\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}\text{L}$)

Sl. no.	Chelates	R_m (Obsd.) (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	${}^1\chi$	${}^1\chi^v$	${}^2\chi^v$	${}^3\chi_p^v$	${}^3\chi_c^v$
1.	Et ₂ Tl(trop)	46.35	5.17	5.97	3.50	2.02	1.65
2.	Et ₂ Tl(Ox)	69.99	6.49	6.11	3.38	1.75	0.78
3.	Et ₂ Tl(dbzm)	91.67	10.67	8.66	4.41	2.38	0.67
4.	Me ₂ Tl(acac) ^d	38.52	4.45	3.94	2.68	1.18	0.80
5.	Me ₂ Tl(sal) ^d	47.24	3.84	4.15	2.53	0.95	0.76

Regression up to ${}^3\chi_c^v$ is not done due to short of equivalent equations. Here, trop = tropolonate, C₇H₅O₂⁻; Ox = oxinate or 8-hydroxyquinolinolate, C₉H₆NO⁻; dbzm = dibenzoyl methanate, C₁₅H₁₁O₂⁻; acac = acetyl acetate, C₅H₇O₂⁻; sal = salicylaldehyde ligand, C₇H₅O₂⁻.

$$R_m = 2.6816 {}^1\chi + 14.0349 {}^1\chi^v + 5.8509 {}^2\chi^v - 33.2173 {}^3\chi_p^v - 4.1605.$$

$$n = 5, r = 1.0000, s = -1.6764e - 08, \text{ P.E. in } r = -1.6961e - 09.$$

Table 4. Molar refraction and ${}^m\chi_t^y$ terms for stepwise regression analysis ($R_2Sn^{IV}L_2$)

Sl. no.	Chelates	R_m (Obsd.) ($cm^3 mol^{-1}$)	${}^1\chi$	${}^1\chi^v$	${}^2\chi^v$	${}^3\chi_p^v$	${}^3\chi_c^v$	${}^4\chi_p^v$
1.	$Me_2SnCl_2(phen)$	105.70	7.11	6.61	3.87	1.71	0.54	0.92
2.	$Me_2SnCl_2(bpy)$	73.17	4.97	6.19	2.70	1.24	0.79	0.64
3.	$Et_2Sn(Ox)_2$	110.77	11.84	8.79	4.86	2.17	1.18	1.80
4.	$Bu_2Sn(trop)_2$	94.12	12.82	9.82	6.08	4.29	0.64	0.60
5.	$Bu_2Sn(Ox)_2$	125.64	14.75	11.40	6.11	3.33	1.34	1.63
6.	$Bu_2Sn(dbzm)_2$	201.76	18.32	16.15	8.81	4.40	1.17	1.88
7.	$Bu_2Sn(sal)_2$	114.22	10.95	9.80	5.16	3.05	0.81	1.38
8.	$n-Oct_2.Sn(Ox)_2$	162.76	18.43	15.36	8.93	5.11	0.83	2.98
9.	$n-Oct_2.Sn(dbzm)_2$	179.31	20.68	20.01	12.66	6.22	0.69	3.30

${}^m\chi_c^y$ and ${}^4\chi_{CH}^y$ terms have been ignored.

$$R_m = 27.7133 \chi - 57.0189 \chi^v + 63.7918 \chi^v - 10.0009 \chi_p^v + 48.0965 \chi_c^v + 11.4387 \chi_p^v.$$

$$n = 9, r = 1.0000, s = 5.6159e - 07. P.E. in r = -4.2088e - 08.$$

ring. Amidon and Anik¹⁵ used this modification term in treating hydrocarbon solubility data.

One approach of valence delta, δ^v has been introduced¹⁶ with the objective to develop valence values for hetero atoms that are non-empirical in the sense of formal connectivity and consonant with the underlying electronic structures of hetero atoms in molecules. Thus, $\delta_i^v = z^v - h_i$; where z^v is the number of valence electrons and h_i is the number of hydrogen atoms suppressed. The ${}^m\chi_t^y$ terms have been calculated in the same way as ${}^m\chi_t$ terms have been calculated, after labelling vertices by δ_i^v instead of δ_i . Valence delta for Tl^{III} and Sn^{IV} have been calculated for the first time. The ${}^m\chi_t^y$ terms, R_m values and regression analysis using a US-package of computer program have been shown in Tables 1-4 for substrates, ligands and chelates respectively.

Results and discussion

The molar refraction, R_m has already been correlated¹⁷ to a series of local anesthetics. Organotin compounds have been studied recently by Laughlin *et al.*¹⁸ and Vighi and Calamari¹⁹. In the former study, parameters such as molar surface areas have been correlated with LC_{50} values of eight triorganotin compounds. In the latter study ${}^1\chi$ and ${}^1\chi^v$ have been used in characterising the toxicities of fifteen organotin compounds. The best correlation has been achieved using $\log(1/EC_{50})$ values regressed with a single parameter ${}^1\chi^v$. In present studies, use of valence delta δ^v improve the quality of correlation of R_m with

${}^m\chi_t^y$ terms. Here, δ_N^v , δ_{Tl}^v or δ_{Sn}^v have not been taken as independent variable in the regression analysis.

Acknowledgement

Dr. Sunanda Das and Dr. Arti Gupta thank UGC, New Delhi for providing financial support to minor research project.

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